

TITLE: Oral cancer awareness among dental students in a private university setting.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: There is a great deal of research on the awareness of students and professionals regarding oral cancer. The aim of this study was to find out students' opinions in their final years of dental school training who have clinic time about the importance of a correct mucosal examination of the oral cavity.

Material and methods: A cross-sectional study was carried out and a questionnaire was designed and distributed to fourth and fifth-year dental students. The questionnaire included demographic aspects of the participants and five closed questions related to the importance given to the exploration of the soft tissues during patient visits, the importance of the university training received, their interest in continuing education in this subject, their role as dentists in early diagnosis and whether they consider themselves prepared to diagnose oral cancer.

Results: 214 undergraduate dental students participated in the study, 24.3% fourth year and 75.7% fifth year. 97.7% of the students considered soft tissue examination to be important or very important. 90.2% of the students surveyed considered the university training received to be important or very important. 66.4% of the students considered that the most qualified professional to diagnose an oral lesion is the dentist.

Conclusions: In this study most students felt that graduate training about oral cancer is important, as well as soft tissue examination. In addition, the majority considered that the professional most indicated to diagnose oral lesions is the dentist. However, a very small percentage felt prepared to diagnose oral cancer themselves.

KEY WORDS: Oral cancer, potentially malignant disorders, students, university education.

INTRODUCTION

Oral cancer mainly develops in the lip and oral cavity, with oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) being the most frequent in 90% of cases¹. In Spain, 55,057 deaths from oral cavity and oropharyngeal cancer were registered between 1979 and 2018¹. Its survival rate is 45-50% at 5 years, being able to reach 80% if diagnosed in early stages². Early diagnosis of the disease is therefore essential³.

In order to achieve early diagnosis of OSCC, the dentist will need to be able to control the risk factors of the disease and detect lesions early. In addition, the patient should be made aware that OSCC exists and that the dentist could be the first professional to detect it. This will require encouraging primary and secondary prevention of the disease during graduate education, as well as continuing education of professionals throughout their working life⁴.

Dentists should be aware that tobacco and alcohol are the classic risk factors for oral cancer, but there are other factors such as betel chewing, human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, exposure to solar radiation, inadequate diets, and poor oral hygiene^{2,5-8}. It is essential that the practitioner is aware that exposure to multiple risk factors increases the risk of oral cancer and, as such, can expose this to patients⁸. The promotion of healthy habits by dentists, including even smoking cessation methods or urging HPV vaccination, should be part of their direct competencies as health professionals^{1,3,9}.

The dentist should be able to detect and refer early premalignant or malignant conditions detected in the oral cavity and refer early any lesion suspicious for malignancy⁸. For this purpose, a correct visual and tactile examination of the mucosa and cervical palpation of possible adenopathies should be performed^{3,9}.

According to the study by López-Jornet et al, 100% of the dentists consulted stated the need to receive training programs in order to improve early detection of oral cancer. They also show that insufficient knowledge about oral cancer is directly related to the delay in its diagnosis³. The dentist's knowledge of his or her role in relation to oral cancer is determined by his or her university training. The academic curriculum of the degree in dentistry places great emphasis on primary and secondary prevention of the disease. It is of paramount importance that professors instill in students their professional role in relation to this disease.

Students of the degree in dentistry at our Institution receive training on oral cancer in the subjects Oral Medical and Surgical Pathology II and III in the third and fourth years respectively.

There are several studies examining the knowledge and awareness of patients, dental students and professionals and other students and healthcare professionals towards OSCC in different countries^{3-5,9-18}. The aim of this study is to find out students' opinions in their final years of dental training (fourth

and fifth years) who are in contact with patients in the clinic on the importance of oral cavity examination during patient visits. In addition, their opinion will be sought on the university training received, on the continuing education courses and on their professional preparation.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

a. Study participants

A cross-sectional study was carried out on the oral cancer awareness of fourth- and fifth-year students of the Degree in Dentistry. The study was carried out by means of an online questionnaire in the month of June 2022.

The number of potential participants was 460, with 232 in the 4th year and 228 in the 5th year.

b. Ethical permission

The study was approved by the local Ethics Committee on May 25th, 2022 and was assigned the internal code CIPI/22.198. Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous. Students were informed verbally and in writing of the nature of the study and were asked to sign an informed consent before beginning the survey. They were also informed that participating in the project would not influence their final grade in any subject.

c. Data collection and survey items

An online questionnaire was developed using the Microsoft Forms[®] digital platform, which was sent to the fourth- and fifth-year students of Dentistry during the month of June 2022.

The questionnaire included demographic aspects of the participants (gender and academic year) and five closed questions related to the importance they give to soft tissue examination in patient visits, the importance of university training received in the early diagnosis of oral cancer, their interest in continuing education on this subject, their role as dental professionals in early diagnosis and whether they consider themselves prepared to diagnose oral cancer. Each question presented four response options, of which only one had to be chosen.

d. Statistical analysis

For qualitative variables, absolute and relative frequencies were calculated. Subsequently, the Chi-square test was used to calculate whether there was a relationship between the answers given according to sex and to the year in training to which the students belonged. A confidence level of 95% was established. The analysis was performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics 22 package.

RESULTS

A total of 214 undergraduate dental students participated in the study, 52 from fourth year (24.3%) and 162 from fifth year (75.7%) with a response rate of 46.52%. 55.6% were women and 44.4% were men. All of them signed the informed consent to take part in the study.

Table 1 shows the responses of the 214 students to the questions in the questionnaire.

Most students (97.7%) considered soft tissue examination important or very important. Similarly, a large majority (90.2%) considered the university training received in relation to the early diagnosis of oral cancer to be important or very important.

Of the students, 44.85% said that they would do continuing education courses on oral cancer whenever possible in the future.

66.4% considered that the most qualified professional to diagnose an oral lesion was the dentist and in second place (23.8%) was the maxillofacial surgeon. To a lesser extent the dermatologist (6.07%) and the general practitioner (3.73%).

50.5% felt that they need more training on oral cancer to be properly prepared to diagnose OSCC. Only 4.2% of the trainees felt prepared to diagnose oral cancer and 39.2% doubted their preparedness.

When comparing the responses provided to the different questions between males and females, all comparisons were non-significant, with responses between male and female students being similar (Table 2). When the responses were compared between fourth year and fifth year students, no differences were found either, the comparisons were not significant in each of the questions (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

The role of the dentist is fundamental in the prevention and early detection of oral cancer in order to reduce mortality and morbidity and improve the patient's quality of life. In addition, the easy accessibility of this disease in the oral cavity facilitates routine examination by the professional at each patient's visit to the dentist. Dentists' awareness and knowledge of oral cancer will depend on the mandatory training on this subject provided by dental schools and on the continuing education that the professional acquires on a voluntary basis after graduation.

The aim of this study was to determine the importance given to oral cancer by fourth- and fifth-year dental students, who are in contact with patients during clinical practice and who have taken the

subjects of Oral Medical and Surgical Pathology II and III. In order to compare the results of the articles reviewed, it should be considered that each university has a different curriculum and that to date there is no single gold-standard questionnaire that has been carried out in all universities ¹².

a. Importance of soft tissue examination.

Students should be educated and trained during their university education on the importance of performing systematic and routine oral examinations of patients for signs of oral cancer ^{13,14}.

97.7% of the students in our study considered soft tissue examination important or very important. These figures could resemble those of Frola and Barrios ¹², who found that 79.3% of their students stated that they routinely examined the oral mucosa of their patients. In contrast is the study by Joseph et al. ¹⁵, in which 95.9% of the students stated that early detection significantly improved the survival of OSCC, but only 20.5% were aware that visual examination is the most effective screening method for this. Remarkably, the results of the research by Keser et al conducted with Turkish students ¹⁶, in which only 3.5% stated that they were adequately prepared to perform oral cancer screening and only 12.1% considered that they were correctly trained to perform a lymph node examination.

b. Importance of university training received.

90.2% of the students surveyed considered the university training received in relation to the early diagnosis of oral cancer to be important or very important. In the literature reviewed, students report having a good attitude towards oral cancer, but stress the need to incorporate more training in the curriculum on diagnosis of oral lesions, including OSCC and PMOS ^{4,10,13,14,18}.

This would involve having more collaboration with other entities such as hospitals, so that students can see more cases directly ¹⁴. In the Hassona et al. study, students reported seeing few cases of oral mucosal lesions ⁴. Along the same lines, access could be provided to observe or perform biopsies, fill out reports to the pathologist, and learn how to interpret the anatomopathology report ¹⁵. In the study by Joseph et al. ¹⁵, only 2.7% of the students exposed having attended the performance of a biopsy.

Furthermore, it is paramount to enhance disease prevention training in order to educate patients regarding oral mucosal lesions ^{14,15,18}. In several studies students exposed that only smoking was emphasized, when there are more risk factors related to oral lesions ^{4,10,12,15}. In the study by Keser et al ¹⁶, it is proposed to update the health questionnaires completed by patients in universities and

hospitals by including every possible emerging risk factor for oral cancer. According to Awan et al, it is vital to educate professionals so that they can teach patients to self-examine the oral mucosa, with a view that changes can be detected, and early diagnosis improved ¹⁰.

Another point to highlight is the need to have a greater number of teachers in clinical practices with patients with oral mucosal lesions ¹⁴, as well as providing more time during clinical practice to be able to learn how to carry out a complete oral diagnosis, emphasizing the soft tissues and not just looking at the teeth ^{12,14,15}.

Despite the limitations in university graduate training, the results of the study by Seoane et al. should be highlighted ¹⁷ in which it was noted that those recently graduated professionals (less than 10 years practicing after leaving university) had received better theoretical training related to OSCC compared to older professionals. In fact, the longer they had been in clinical practice, the less mucosal examination of patients and, consequently, the less biopsies were performed ¹⁷.

c. Opinion on the need for continuing education.

Apart from the United States, where continuing education is mandatory for dentists, comparing the knowledge of North American dentists and those of the rest of the world is not uniform ¹⁷. In the rest of the countries, it is considered a moral duty of the professional to be trained to be able to diagnose a precancerous condition or even a carcinoma in situ ¹⁷. In our case, 98.6% of the students said that they would consider the option of attending continuing education courses on the subject once they had completed their university training.

The reality is that continuing education courses on OSCC would be very useful, above all, to improve its prevention ¹⁷. These courses should include how to perform oral examinations correctly and biopsies ¹⁷.

d. Perception of the most qualified professional to diagnose oral lesions.

The results of our study show that 66.4% of the students considered that the professional most qualified to diagnose an oral lesion is the dentist and in second place, with 23.8%, the maxillofacial surgeon. To a lesser extent, the dermatologist (6.07%) and the general practitioner (3.73%). These results could be justified if we consider that the dentist and the maxillofacial surgeon are the professionals with the best instruments, equipment (dental chair) and lighting for exploring the oral cavity. The percentage of patients who come to the dentist is significantly higher than those who

consult the maxillofacial surgeon for the first time, so surely it should be the dentist who is more likely to diagnose a suspicious lesion in the oral cavity. It should not be forgotten that many of the patients at higher risk for oral cancer may regularly come to the general practitioner for various ailments and not be properly explored, and oral premalignant lesions may remain undiagnosed ¹⁰.

There are studies that compare the knowledge of oral cancer between dental and medical students. In them, better results are obtained in relation to knowledge, attitude and practice in dental students ⁵. In the study by Awan et al. ¹⁰, statistically significant differences were obtained in favor of dental students compared to medical students, when contrasting the systematic exploration of the oral mucosa, identification of risk factors and changes in the oral mucosa associated with cancer (leukoplakia and erythroplakia).

e. Perception about the ability to diagnose oral cancer.

50.5% of our students consider that they need more training on oral cancer in order to be correctly prepared to diagnose OSCC. This figure increases to 70% in the study by Bhagavathula et al. ¹¹, in which students exposed not having enough knowledge about prevention and detection of OSCC. In fact, 95% considered additional training on the topic necessary.

Only 4.2% of the students felt prepared to diagnose oral cancer and 39.2% doubted their preparedness. The fact that students do not feel confident in diagnosing oral lesions could have a direct impact on the delay of early diagnosis of the disease. Thus, in the studies by Shubayr et al ¹⁸ and Joseph et al ¹⁵, students stated that, when faced with a suspected OSCC lesion, they would choose to refer it to the maxillofacial surgery department (53% and 31.5%, respectively) or to the specialty in Oral Medicine (47% and 47.9%, respectively).

As can be seen, OSCC is a complex pathology, involving many healthcare professionals, so collaboration between oral and maxillofacial surgeons, otolaryngologists, plastic surgeons, oncologists and dentists should be enhanced ¹⁰.

f. Limitations of the study.

This study has some limitations that should be taken into consideration. The study was carried out by undergraduate students at a single university and the data cannot be extrapolated to a region. The subjectivity of the students' responses should be considered since the aim was to find out their opinion on specific aspects of oral cancer. It would be interesting to carry out multicenter studies that would make it possible to establish the necessary curricular adaptations in subjects on oral cancer.

In addition, the response rate was 46.52%, which adds a selection bias to the study.

CONCLUSION

In this study, most of the students considered that university education on oral cancer is important, as well as the exploration of soft tissues. In addition, most of them considered that the most appropriate professional to diagnose oral lesions is the dentist. However, a very small percentage feel prepared to diagnose oral cancer.

Oral cancer is a disease with a high mortality rate that requires future dentists to be knowledgeable about its prevention by educating patients on smoking and alcohol cessation, promotion of good oral hygiene and early detection of premalignant conditions. But to do so, they must be aware of the crucial role they play. This leads to giving them more weight in the academic curriculum and encouraging further training courses.

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TABLES

Table 1. Number (n) and percentage (%) of responses to each question in the questionnaire.

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Question 1. What importance do you place on soft tissue examination in patient visits?		
	n	%
Not important	1	0.46
Slightly important	4	1.89
Important	81	37.85
Very important	128	59.81
Question 2. What importance do you place on the university training received in relation to an early diagnosis of oral cancer?		
	n	%
Not important	4	1.86
Slightly important	17	7.94
Important	94	43.92
Very important	99	46.26
Question 3. Are you considering attending continuing education courses about oral cancer and potentially malignant disorders in the future?		
	n	%
I will assist continuing education courses whenever I can.	96	44.85
I am very interested in the subject. In fact, I will try to specialize in it.	40	18.69
It is possible I will attend some training courses.	75	35.04
I consider I have enough training and I do not need it.	3	1.40
Question 4. Who do you think should be the most qualified professional to diagnose an oral mucosal lesion?		
	n	%
General practitioner	8	3.73
Dermatologist	13	6.07
Dentist	142	66.35
Maxillofacial surgeon	51	23.83
Question 5. Do you consider that you would be prepared to diagnose oral cancer in your clinical practice?		
	n	%
Not prepared.	13	6.07
I will need more training to be ready.	108	50.46
Maybe I am ready.	84	39.25
Well-prepared.	9	4.2

Table 2. A comparison between fourth vs. fifth year dental students and males vs. females.

TABLE 2. A comparison between fourth vs. fifth year dental students and males vs. females.						
	4th-year n (%)	5th-year n (%)	p	Males n (%)	Females n (%)	p
Question 1. What importance do you place on soft tissue examination in patient visits?						
Not important	0 (0)	1 (0.6)	0.208	0 (0)	1 (0.8)	0.659
Slightly important	0 (0)	4 (2.5)		1 (1)	3 (2.5)	
Important	15 (28.8)	66 (40.7)		35 (36.8)	46 (38.7)	
Very important	37 (71.2)	91 (56.2)		59 (62.1)	69 (58)	
Question 2. What importance do you place on the university training received in relation to an early diagnosis of oral cancer?						
Not important	2 (3.8)	2 (1.2)	0.095	1 (1.1)	3 (2.5)	0.167
Slightly important	1 (1.9)	16 (9.9)		5 (5.3)	12 (10.1)	
Important	20 (38.5)	74 (45.7)		49 (51.6)	45 (37.8)	
Very important	29 (55.8)	70 (43.2)		40 (42.1)	59 (49.6)	
Question 3. Are you considering attending continuing education courses about oral cancer and potentially malignant disorders in the future?						
I will assist continuing education courses whenever I can.	22 (42.3)	74 (45.7)	0.790	42 (44.2)	54 (45.4)	0.618
I am very interested in the subject. In fact, I will try to specialize in it.	12 (23.1)	28 (17.3)		15 (15.8)	25 (21)	
It is possible I will attend some training courses.	17 (32.7)	58 (35.8)		36 (37.9)	39 (32.8)	
I consider I have enough training and I do not need it.	1 (1.9)	2 (1.2)		2 (2.1)	1 (0.8)	
Question 4. Who do you think should be the most qualified professional to diagnose an oral mucosal lesion?						
General practitioner.	1 (1.9)	7 (4.3)	0.268	4 (4.2)	4 (3.4)	0.234
Dermatologist.	4 (7.7)	9 (5.6)		7 (7.4)	6 (5)	
Dentist.	30 (57.7)	112 (69.1)		56 (58.9)	86 (72.3)	
Maxillofacial surgeon.	17 (32.7)	34 (21.0)		28 (29.5)	23 (19.3)	
Question 5. Do you consider that you would be prepared to diagnose oral cancer in your clinical practice?						
Not prepared.	4 (7.7)	9 (5.6)	0.565	6 (6.3)	7 (5.9)	0.195
I will need more training to be ready.	22 (42.3)	86 (53.1)		41 (43.2)	67 (56.3)	
Maybe I am ready.	23 (44.2)	61 (37.7)		42 (44.2)	42 (35.3)	
Well-prepared.	3 (5.8)	6 (3.7)		6 (6.3)	3 (2.5)	